

CONNECTION WITH EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES IN FORMING EDUCATION

(In the case of technology lessons)

Olimov Bakhtiorjon Usmanovich

Kokan State Pedagogical Institute, Associate Professor

baxtiyorjonolimov7206@gmail.com

ANNOTATION In this article, the current tasks before the technical science of general secondary schools and the psychological, pedagogical and technical-technological aspects of the educational process, the use of interdisciplinary links in the educational process and general secondary education are discussed. Many organizational, legal and scientific research works are being carried out on reforming the system, improving teaching technologies, forming modern knowledge and skills in students, using new teaching methods for this purpose. Through this, it is aimed to create a system of training a generation of competitive and high-potential personnel. This makes the formation of creativity-related skills in students one of the urgent tasks. That's why, on the basis of innovative tools, thoughts and opinions about the need to develop creative abilities in young people have been discussed.

Keywords. project, design, creative person, creativity, creative thinking, ability, creative abilities.

KIRISH The issue of creating a system for developing students' creative abilities is becoming urgent in the world. Education of a creative person based on the possibilities of STEAM sciences, which play an important role in the development

of modern society in the world education experience - science, technology, engineering, design (art), and mathematics, is a priority. is defined as Also, UNESCO's report "The Future of Jobs" released in October 2020 stated that critical thinking and creativity will be among the top five skills in demand by 2025. . Therefore, improving the theoretical foundations of the development of creative abilities of students in the international educational space is considered as one of the important socio-pedagogical tasks. In the world's developed scientific research institutes and international centers, a lot of scientific and research work is being carried out in order to reveal the hidden abilities of students, to improve the tools of influence aimed at developing the skills that are required today. The developed countries of the world are setting themselves the task of not only increasing production, but also transitioning to an innovative economy based on deep knowledge and scientific achievements. That is why the development of one's economy by creating innovative products, mastering and introducing advanced technologies into development is considered as the main factor of development. Such social changes increase the demand for educating students who are creative, critical thinkers, who can quickly solve problems and quickly adapt to situations from the modernized general secondary education system.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS Based on this, in general secondary schools of technology classes in the direction of "Technology and design" by means of design projects, the problems related to the formation of creative abilities of students are purposefully researched, which constitute its content and essence, and it is necessary to select and systematize the necessary forms, methods and tools of the field of education, which are compatible with the educational program, on a scientific basis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION When organizing the process of teaching students in technology classes, it is necessary to determine the content of the situation and correctly direct it. Conditions are created for the student to study the educational materials specified in the DTS. In order to acquire practical skills, the student needs to complete the mastering labor exercises and the initial tasks oriented to production. In order to implement this process, the methodological guide for students will be directed to methodological recommendations and educational goals. In this process, students have to do something independently. This process is important. In the conditions of students' deeper penetration into technology education, they lack the knowledge and skills of Physics and Chemistry. Because in technology education, understanding the harmful effects of a substance, physical changes in the process of making something allows them not to put their health at risk. "It is necessary to know their physical properties before working with various materials in practical training on technology education. The property of a substance to maintain its chemical composition as a result of external influence is called its physical properties. Such properties include such properties as color, density, solubility, heat resistance, heat capacity, thermal and electrical conductivity, and magnetism. For example, when a metal is heated, its composition does not change when heat or electric current passes through it, when it is magnetically affected. The physical properties of metal are very useful in distinguishing them from each other and using them. For example, any metal has its own luster, which is called its color. Not all metals are the same color. For example, copper is red, tin is shiny white, zinc is gray, and steel is light blue. It can be noted here that metals change color when oxidized in air, and even the thinnest piece of metal does not transmit light. When a material is heated, it quickly transfers heat from itself is called its thermal conductivity. The faster the

metal conducts heat, the faster and more evenly it heats up and cools down. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the possibility of their dimensions changing due to heat during the manufacture and processing of metal products. In general, it is possible to distinguish materials according to their physical properties, to choose alternatives, and to prepare details and parts of the product" [5]. In addition to these, it is necessary to make wide use of physical concepts such as types of movement, force, pressure, power, energy, work, and friction in making various items from materials with the help of basic tools or machines, adjusting tools, in technology lessons.

SUMMARY In conclusion, technology education aims to develop the skills of making the right choice in choosing a profession based on the formation of creativity in students. For example, "in the 5th-7th grades, information is mainly given about the profession. Pupils will get acquainted with what public working professions exist. Elements of these professions form the content of students' activities in the workshop. This situation fully corresponds to the task of general technical training of students in this period of education. In the 6th grade, and especially in the 7th grade, along with providing information about the profession, vocational training is also carried out. The reason for this is that on the eve of graduation of the 7th grade, students need to choose the profile (direction) of future labor training. Each profile includes many public worker occupations. These can be professions that are consistently related to the content of workshop training (for example, professions related to metal and wood, gas processing) or professions that have nothing to do with them»[6]. However, in the work experience of schools, it is possible to observe such a situation that teachers try to solve this issue depending on the mastery of students, that is, excellent students are given the right to choose, and poor masters

are forced to choose one of the remaining professions. they eat In conclusion, "technology" education in general secondary education has a positive effect on the development of creativity skills in students along with hard work. Therefore, it is important to feel the working environment, the process of creating techniques and technologies, and to increase their knowledge about their use in the formation of students' creativity skills.

ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Yangi O‘zbekiston strategiyasi. –Toshkent.: O‘zbekiston. 2021. –B. 238
2. O‘quv dasturlarini uzviylikini rivojlantirish – ta’lim sifatini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. 14.09.2020 <http://marifat.uz/marifat/ruknlar/umumii-urta-talim/4889.htm>
3. Lerner I.Ya. Didakticheskie osnovy metodov obucheniya. Moskva : Pedagogika, 1981. – S.48. [Lerner I.Ya. Didactic foundations of teaching methods. Moscow : Pedagogika, 1981. – p.48.]
4. Karimov I. O‘quvchilarning ijodkorlik faoliyatini tashkil etish. //Xalq ta’limi j.,-Toshkent. 2010 yil 4-soni. –B. 58-59.
5. Karimov I. Mehnat ta’limida o‘quvchilar ijodkorlik faoliyatini tashkil etishning uyg‘unlashgan texnologiyalari: Monografiya. T.: Adabiyot uchqunlari, 2015. – b. 139. [Karimov I. Harmonized technologies for organizing the activities of creativity of students in labor education: monograph. T.: Sparks of literature, 2015. - b. 139]
6. Tohirov O‘.O. Texnologiya o‘quv fani davlat ta’lim standarti va o‘quv dasturini ta’lim amaliyotiga joriy etish metodikasi. // Metodik tavsiyanoma. –Toshkent. : RTM, 2017. –B.65. [Tahirav O`.O. Technology educational science is a state educational standard and a methodology for introducing the curriculum into

educational practice. // Methodological recommendation. - Tashkent. : RTM, 2017. –B.65]

REFERENCES

1. Toxirov, U. O., & Tursunov, J. E. (2012). Voprosy formirovaniya metodologicheskix, kognitivnyx i kreativnyx kachestv uchashixsya. In *Pedagogika: traditsii i innovatsii* (pp. 112-113).
2. Tursunov, J. E. (2021). *EFFEKTIVNYYE SPOSOBY OPREDELENIY_a KREATIVNYX SPOSOBNOSTEY UChASHIXSY_a NA UROKAX TEXNOLOGII*. In *SOVREMENNYE NAUCHNYYE ISSLEDOVANIY_a: AKTUALNYYE VOPROSY, DOSTIJENIY_a I INNOVATSII* (pp. 153-157).
3. Tursunov, J. E. (2018). V-VII sinflar mehnat ta'limi mashg'ulotlarida o'quvchilar kreativlik qobiliyatlarini shakllantirish modeli. *Sovremennoe obrazovanie (Uzbekistan)*, (1), 12-20.
4. Tursunov, J. (2011). Ispolzovanie texnologii evristicheskix obuchayushix situatsiy v razvitiy kreativnyx sposobnostey uchashixsya. *Molodoy uchenyy*, (11-2), 177-178.
5. BAyBoBoEV, N. G., XAMZAEV, A. A., & RAXMoNoV, X. T. (2014). Raschet kineticheskoy energii prutkovogo elevatora s sentrobejnoj separatsiey. *Vestnik Ryazanskogo gosudarstvennogo agrotexnologicheskogo universiteta im. PA Kostycheva*, (2), 19-21.
6. Bayboboev, N. G., Byshov, N. V., Borыchev, S. N., Muxamedov, J. M., Raxmonov, X. T., Akbarov, Sh. B., ... & Rembalovich, G. K. (2019). *Navesnaya separiruyushaya mashina*.

7. Zaparov, A., Rakhmonov, K., & Isakova, Z. (2021). Modular Teaching Technology In Technical Sciences Application Methodology. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(3), 349-355.
8. Raxmonov, X. T. (2018). SUBSTANTIATING THE PARAMETERS OF CLOUDS-DESTRUCTING BODY OF THE INTEGRATED ASSEMBLY. *Scientific-technical journal*, 1(2), 127-130.
9. Sotvoldiyev, E., Khamdamova, V., Ibragimova, M., & Usmanova, M. (2020). PREPARING STUDENTS FOR BUSINESS ACTIVITY IN SCHOOL TECHNOLOGY CLASSES. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(2), 1-4.
10. Ibragimova, M., Yusufkhodjaeva, F., Sattorova, D., & Sotvoldiyev, E. TECHNOLOGY OF USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN SCHOOL EDUCATION.
11. Isakova, Z. (2018). MEJPPREDMETNAYa PREEMSTVENNOST SREDNE-SPESSIONOGO I VYISSHEGO OBRAZOVANIYa. *Aktualnye nauchnye issledovaniya v sovremennom mire*, (12-4), 59-63.
12. Xonboboev, X. O., Ikromova, M. X., & Ikromov, M. A. X. (2016). Ta'limda axborot texnologiyalarni qollashning oziga xos xususiyatlari. *Molodoy uchenyy*, (3-1), 21-22.
13. MUBINAKHON, I., & ANASKHON, I. M. The Importance of Using the Ict to Increase the Efficiency of Education. *JournalNX*, 7(1), 106-108.
14. Yusufxodjaeva, F. M. (2018). Tarbiya usullarini to'g'ri tanlashning ta'lim jarayonidagi ahamiyati. *Sovremennoe obrazovanie (Uzbekistan)*, (1), 52-59.
15. Yusufxodjaeva, F. (2018). OSNOVY OBRAZOVATELNOY PRAKTIKI PYaTIKLASSNIKOV OBIЩEOBRAZOVATELNYX ShKOL. *Aktualnye nauchnye issledovaniya v sovremennom mire*, (5-6), 44-46.

16. Yusufxodjaeva, F. M. (2019). Kasbiy mahorat va kompetentlikni rivojlantirish jarayonida motivlashtirish. *Sovremennoe obrazovanie (Uzbekistan)*, (1 (74)), 11-17.
17. Sobirovna, U. M., & Irodaxon, T. (2022). TEXNOLOGIYA FANI MASHG'ULOTLARINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH METODLARI. *PEDAGOGS* jurnali, 21(1), 41-44.
18. Sobirovna, U. M. (2022). Improving the educational system for children with disabilities. *The Peerian Journal*, 4, 20-22.
19. Yusufkhodjaeva, F., Usmanova, M., Sattorova, D., & Khamdamova, V. THE USE OF ICT IN SCHOOL EDUCATION. *computer*, 1, 104.
20. Maryam, I., & Mukhlisa, U. The Use of Interactive Methods in the Orientation of Students to Entrepreneurial Activity. *JournalNX*, 7(03), 223-226.
21. Ibragimova, M. G. (2022). METHODS OF INVENTING YOUNG PEOPLE TO ENTREPRENEURSHIP THROUGH INTERACTIVE METHODS. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(2), 45-48.
22. Ibragimova, M. G., Hamdamova, V. A., & Yusufxodjaeva, F. M. (2020). YoShLARNI IQTISODIY TARBIYALASHDA TEJAMKORLIKNING O'RNI. *Internauka*, (23-3), 61-62.
23. Ibragimova, M. G. (2019). NOVIYE TEXNOLOGII SHITYA V TRUDOVOM OBUChENII. *Aktualnye nauchnye issledovaniya v sovremennom mire*, (2-5), 113-116.
24. Ibragimova, M. G. (2011). Faktory moralno-nravstvennogo orientirovaniya uchashixsya professionalnyx kolledjey na predprinimatelskuyu deyatel'nost. *Molodoy uchenyy*, (12-2), 99-101.
25. Ibragimova Mariyam G'ulomovna (2019). Iqtisodii muzokaralar jaraenida tanqidiy fikrlashga yo'naltirilgan pedagogik metodlar ahamiyati. *Sovremennoe obrazovanie (Uzbekistan)*, (1 (74)), 18-24.

26. Tojiyevich, R. X., Juraevich, X. A., & Toshpo'latovich, Y. O. (2022). Theoretical Justification Of The Dimensions Of The Working Part Of The Combined Aggregate Cutting Grinder. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(9), 3663-3667.
27. Toshpulatovich, Y. O. (2021). SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNOLOGICAL BASIS OF POTATO DEVELOPMENT. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 296-300.
28. Yuldashev, O. T. (2018). Umumiy o'rta ta'lim, oliy ta'lim tizimida mehnat ta'limi darslarini tashkil etishda integratsiya jarayonining o'rni. *Sovremennoe obrazovanie (Uzbekistan)*, (1), 35-43.
29. Zaparov, A., Rakhmonov, K., & Isakova, Z. (2021). Modular Teaching Technology In Technical Sciences Application Methodology. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(3), 349-355.
30. Abdurahmonov, S. H., Bo'taev, A., & Zokirov, V. (2022). TECHNICAL CREATIVITY GEOMETRICGRAPHIC DESIGN IN STUDENTS DEVELOPMENT BASED ON EXERCISE. *Conferencea*, 140-145.
31. Butaev, A. A., Isakova, Z. R., & Zaparov, A. (2021). THE METHODS OF DEVELOPING MODERN TECHNOLOGY SKILLS AMONG GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOL PUPILS. *Ekonomika i sotsium*, (2-1), 112-114.
32. Baratboyev, B., Butayev, A., & Mamadiyev, U. (2019). THE USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE TEACHING OF FINE ARTS. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 7(12).
33. Butaev, A., & Abduraxmanov, Sh. (2011). Razvitie kriticheskogo myshleniya cherez prostranstvennoe predstavlenie i texnicheskoe risovanie. *Molodoy uchenyy*, (11-2), 151-154.

34. Farruxovna, B. G., & Ashirovich, B. A. Pedagogical and Psychological Factors in the Membership of Individual Interest in the System of Continuous Education. *JournalNX*, 7(04), 388-391.
35. Ashirovich, B. A. To Develop The Ability of Thinking Creatively of Students in The Process of Drawing.
36. Zikrillaev, N. F., Saitov, E. B., Tursunov, O. B., Khusanov, A. J., & Kurbonaliev, K. K. (2021). Features Of Self-Oscillatory Processes In A Strongly Compensated Silicon With Nanoclusters Of Impurity Atoms. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 8(1), 935-939.
37. Jurayevich, H. A. (2020). Some issues of directing students for independent scientific research. *ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL*, 10(12), 1314-1317.
38. Kamilov, T. S., Kabilov, D. K., Samiev, I. S., Husanov, A. Z., & Dadamuhamedov, S. (2005, June). The thermoelectric radiation detector based on the multielement structures of the higher manganese silicide films. In *ICT 2005. 24th International Conference on Thermoelectrics, 2005*. (pp. 543-545). IEEE.
39. Kamilov, T. S., Xusanov, A. J., Вахадьрханов, М. К., & Kobilov, D. K. (2002). Polikristallicheskie neselektivnye priemniki izlucheniya na osnove plenok vysshego silitsida margansa. *Pisma v JTF*, 28(22).
40. Souma, T., Ohtaki, M., Zhang, Y., Bian, Z., Shakouri, A., Terasaki, I., ... & Dadamuhamedov, S. (2005). Tom. 2005. *Proceedings-ICT'05: 24th International Conference on Thermoelectrics.-Ser. ProceedingsICT'05: 24th International Conference on Thermoelectrics. Evaluation*, 387, 390.

41. Usmonovich, O. B., & Qizi, O. D. B. (2021). FORMATION OF INFORMATION LITERACY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. World Bulletin of Social Sciences, 2, 122-123.
42. Olimov, B. U., & Olimova, D. B. Q. (2021). INNOVATION TA'LIM MUHITIDA O'QUVCHILARNING KITOB O'QISHGA BO'LGAN QIZIQISHLARI YUZASIDAN UZVIYLIK VA UZLUKSIZLIKNI YO'LGA QO'YISH. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(10), 321-325.
43. Olimov, B. U., & Olimova, D. B. (2020). ORGANIZATION OF MENTAL ARITHMETIC COURSES FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. Theoretical & Applied Science, (4), 943-946.
44. Olimov, B. U., & Olimova, D. B. (2020). The effectiveness of mental arithmetic courses in pre-school education. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 02 (82), 525-527.
45. Olimov, B. U., & Olimova, D. B. (2020). ORGANIZATION OF MENTAL ARITHMETICS COURSES FOR EARLY CLASS STUDENTS IN SCHOOLS. Theoretical & Applied Science, (2), 522-524.